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Proposing a Comprehensive Knowledge Map of Engineering Ethics for Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

Engineering has been a preferred discipline in higher education in Asian countries. Approximately 1/4 of students in higher education are studying engineering in Taiwan. In recent years however, several engineering related disasters such as the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Disaster, the sinking of the MV Sewol ferry, and the Kaohsiung Pipeline Explosion, have left a devastating impact on Asian societies. Studying disasters can provide insights to Engineering Ethics, Engineering Ethics can then promote better engineering. This paper is grounded in a collaborative Japanese – Taiwanese effort to provide effective tools for Engineering Ethics education and proposes a conceptual framework for Engineering Ethics in the form of a 4 x 3 dimensional GRID. This GRID is illustrated using the example of the discussion around the Kaohsiung pipeline explosion.

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INTRODUCTION

As a response to engineering failures, Engineering Ethics has developed in the West as an important part of engineering professionalism since the turn of 20th century. Owing to the recent interests in engineering education accreditation in Asia, Engineering Ethics has been recognized as an essential part of engineering education. Engineering Ethics appeared in engineering education in Taiwan only several decades ago, even though the engineering curricula follow the western ones closely. But the big question remains within the engineering community: what is Engineering Ethics and how should one teach it? The Japanese Society of Engineering Education (JSEE) started a discussion around these big questions among domestic and international scholars and published the first version of the Learning and Educational Objectives in 2013, which is renewed annually as reported in Kobayashi & Fudano [1]. The objectives are divided into several categories, which belongs to Cognitive and Affective domains. In the Taiwanese setting, Hong & Wang 2013 [2] discussed their findings about a Science, Technology and Society (STS) approach to Engineering Ethics teaching.

Thereafter, inspired from a survey feedback with Taiwan's engineering ethics educators on the JSEE's Objectives, we constructed a knowledge map, which we hope will be helpful for engineering educators to discuss Engineering Ethics. This knowledge map is represented as a 4x3 GRID of Engineering Ethics, with 4 levels of concern and 3 areas of focus. The levels of concern are micro, meso, macro and meta as proposed in Li [3] and Fudano [4], and they refer to respectively as individual acts, institutional issues, society and engineering issues and the nature of engineering in a general sense. The 3 categories of focus are Educating Engineering (teach and learn), Practicing Engineering (do and make) and Creating Engineering (research and innovate). As an example, we use the GRID to analyse the investigation taking place in the aftermath of the 2014 Kaohsiung pipeline explosion. It is clear that the actions following the disaster focused more on the micro and meso levels whilst reflections about engineering education and discussions about innovative solutions were not explored.

1 ENGINEERING ETHICS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

1.1 General Background

Engineering Ethics has been an important part of engineering professionalism since the turn of the 20th century as a response to engineering failures in the West. Moral values, personal conducts and professional practices are incorporated as part of the Engineering Ethics education in many western engineering educations.

Gardelle [5] discussed that European countries and countries receiving European influences, have made changes in and adaptations to higher education, engineering education and training for engineers as the Lisbon Strategy, the Bologna Process and the project INNOV'ING 2020 took shape. Froyd *et al.* [6] reviewed how Engineering education has gone through several transformations in the 20th century. Ethical education can be included in engineering education and training as discussed in

Monteiro *et al.* [7]; challenges and expectations are different in two subsystems in the Portugal cases.

In Taiwan and Japan, Engineering Ethics appeared in engineering education just several decades ago even though their engineering curricula follow the western ones closely. The long-standing segregation between the aspect of the social/humanity and the aspect of science/technology in education makes it difficult for Engineering Ethics to take roots in engineering education. It is therefore often regarded as an “additional” or “required but trivial” subject.

1.2 Engineering accreditation

As countries with a high number of engineers in training in higher education per capita, Japan and Taiwan have joined the leagues of engineering education accreditation efforts since late 20th century. The Japanese Accreditation Board of Engineering Education (JABEE) and the Institute of Engineering Education Taiwan (IEET) were established respectively in 1999 and 2003 as accreditation organizations in these countries. More than 500 departments in Taiwan have been accredited by IEET criteria since 2003.

1.3 Criteria of Engineering Ethics

Because of the interests of engineering education accreditation in Asia, Engineering Ethics has been recognised as an essential part of engineering education. As required in IEET, *Criterion 3 Graduate Attributes and Assessment*, a program seeking accreditation must demonstrate that students have attended the following outcome upon graduation: “3.7 knowledge of contemporary issues; an understanding of the impact of engineering solutions in an environmental, societal, and global context; and the ability and habit to engage in life-long learning” and “3.8 apply ethical principles and commit to professional ethics and responsibilities and norms of engineering practice, and a sense of respect for diversity”. In other words, these criteria task engineering faculties with the imperative to teach integrated ethical ability in their departments.

1.4 Number of Engineering Ethics courses

Traditionally, Taiwanese curricula do not include ethics, social or other integrated courses. Therefore, many departments either started offering “Engineering Ethics” courses or sought help from humanity scholars. *Fig. 1* and *Fig. 2* show an increase in the number of courses, and in the number of students approximately after 2005. This corresponds to the take-off of the accreditation trend in Taiwan. But the big question remains within the engineering community: what is Engineering Ethics and how should one teach it?

Fig. 1. Number of students have enrolled in Engineering Ethics courses

Fig. 2. Number of Engineering Ethics Courses offered

2 APPROACHES TO ENGINEERING ETHICS TEACHING

2.1 JSEE's teaching and learning Objectives

The Japanese Society of Engineering Education (JSEE) started discussing the big questions among domestics and international scholars and published the first version of Learning and Educational Objectives in 2013, renewed annually thereafter as in Kabayashi & Fudano [1]. The objectives are divided into 2 domains (Cognitive and Affective) and 4 categories. The 4 categories are: (1) Comprehension of the relation between science/technology and society/environment, (2) Comprehension of the role, commitments and responsibilities of engineers, (3) Ability to make ethical judgments and solve problems, and (4) Attitudes required of engineers and values shared by engineers. The first three are in cognitive domain.

2.2 Taiwan's Engineering Ethics educator's responses

Hong and Wang have been studying an STS approach to Engineering Ethics teaching in Taiwan since 2007. In late 2015, they conducted a survey with domestic Engineering Ethics educators asking them about their opinions to the JSEE objectives. Ten percent of 363 instructors who have taught Engineering Ethics courses during 2013~2014 responded to the questionnaire. We asked the educators about how important they regard the JSEE objectives and how important the role is which these issues play in their course work. From the respondents' who gave feedback through this preliminary survey, the educators asked for teaching material based on solid research, especially material which supports interactive teaching. Helping engineering students to develop concerns about social issues and reflective thinking about ethical issues is crucial and challenging. Moreover, there were diverse views about the qualification of the educators of Engineering Ethics. In Taiwan, an estimated more than 80% of the educators are engineering scholars. This situation is very different from Japan, where Engineering Ethics educators mostly comprise social science scholars, including historians of science, philosophers of science and ethics scholars.

3 KNOWLEDGE MAPS FOR ENGINEERING ETHICS

3.1 The Engineering Ethics GRID

Through this review process and the survey on the Objectives, we constructed a knowledge map which we hope will be helpful for discussing Engineering Ethics with engineering educators. We now propose a 4x3 GRID of Engineering Ethics as a framework for engineering education, as shown in Table 1. There are 4 levels of concerns: micro, meso, macro and meta as in Fudano [4], concerning the individual acts, the institutional issues, society and engineering to the nature of engineering. There are 3 categories of focuses: Educating Engineering (teach and learn), Practicing Engineering (do and make) and Creating Engineering (research and innovate).

Table 1. GRID of Engineering Ethics

Category	Engineering Education	Engineering Practices	Engineering Creation
Level \ Action	teach and learn	do and make	research and innovate
Meta The nature of engineering	Engineering Philosophy, ultimate Objectives	Practicing engineering, the nature of industry	Sustainability, for the future / heal the past

Macro Relationship between society and engineering	Engineering teaching in the context of society	Good (real) CSR	Innovation for the needs of society
Meso Institutional issues related to engineering and engineers/organizations	Support for good engineering education, good evaluation strategies and nimble to necessary transformation	Certification and support for establishing good institution practices	Discussion and support to resolve/avoid Issues (research ethics)
Micro Acts of individual engineers/organizations	Curriculum / instruction; pedagogy	Practical skills in industrial setting	Research, design, innovate in the lab/company

3.2 Expected advantages

This GRID can serve as a reference for teaching issues concerning Engineering Ethics as it includes levels from personal to societal in areas of education, industry and academia; allowing the focus to start at any cell and remain aware of the others for discussion of Engineering Ethics under various contexts. Making these issues explicitly visible and unpacking the inter-relationships, this GRID can promote a more sophisticated discussion about dimensions that are often overlooked. It can also be used to track the progress of developments of issues and concerns, and/or benchmark the aftermath of disastrous events. Educators can remind students to pay attention to those unattended perspectives, which may need innovative ideas to resolve.

Although the GRID is laid out as a table, users should note that the division between cells is not definite or rigid, the various factors can interact and affect each other. Also the 3 categories are interconnected as for instance creation has a strong influence on education. We apply the GRID to a study of a recent engineering disaster in the next section, as an example.

3.3 Kaohsiung Pipeline Explosion

Near midnight on July 31st, 2014, sections of main roads in densely populated residential and business neighbourhoods in Kaohsiung city centre exploded, as shown in *Fig. 3*. Thirty-two people were killed and 321 were wounded. Many of the victims were emergency response personnel. Based on the indictment of Kaohsiung District Prosecutors Office, the direct cause of the explosion was a leaky propene pipeline, which was wrongfully exposed in a rainwater culvert box. The erosion caused by the moisture in the culvert box may have weakened the wall of the pipeline, which carried the propene pumped to a petrochemical factory. During the 4 hours between the first reporting of the foul smell around 8pm to the explosion at midnight, an estimated 10 tons of propene leaked into the rainwater culvert boxes beneath the roads before it finally exploded. Emergency response teams and the city government were scrambling and not able to identify what was leaking and they also did not know about the exact location of pipelines going through the city's underground. Citizens were shocked by this apparent lack of information about the pipelines and the chemical as such, as well as the chaotic emergency response about the leak from the first moment the foul smell was noticed up to the moment of the actual explosion.

Fig. 3. Street affected in the Kaohsiung explosion (photo by Syuan Shih Sheng)

What can an engineering disaster of this magnitude teach us? Human beings learn from disasters and failures and then create better regulations, theorems and practices. In Hong and Wang [8], we took an STS approach to the technical characteristics along with ethical reflections. This case revealed that there is a void between the knowledge *about* and the practices *of* civil engineering and petrochemical engineering, especially when it comes to proper documentation and management. It appears that conventional construction work can be very different from the theories taught about this in class and the approved drawings of the work-plans. Many spontaneous decisions were often made on site, and were left out from the documentation. Furthermore, whilst, the petrochemical factory takes safety very seriously within/inside the walls of the factory land. The pipelines running under-ground throughout the city, from the factory to another industrial establishment, are usually not included in their focus on safety procedures. Furthermore, some steps in the highly regulated standard operating procedures (SOP) were set up under assumptions regarding the operation conditions. Since a pipeline leak had never happened before, such an occurrence was therefore not given high priority in the SOP. The public may have had a blind trust in the expertise of the petrochemical industry and City's technological governance. It is very difficult to pursue an understanding about the risk of living in an industrialised city, when knowledge about the industry and its operations are not part of the public domain..

Hong and Wang's research team has been following the court process pertaining to the Kaohsiung pipeline explosion since the companies and the city government were prosecuted with criminal charges in late 2014. We use the GRID to show the aftermath of the explosion in *Table 2*. It can be seen that the efforts after the event focused more on the micro and meso levels about practicing engineering.

When we use the GRID to evaluate Kaohsiung pipeline explosion, it is clear that the investigation focused more on the micro and meso level practices; the core values and the directions regarding a better engineering for society are still to be discussed. It can be seen clearly that reflections on engineering education and discussions about innovative solutions to the problems remained unexplored.

Table 2. Kaohsiung Propene Explosion explained in Engineering Ethics GRID

Category	Engineering Education	Engineering Practices	Engineering Creation
Action	teach and learn	do and make	research and innovate
Meta The nature of engineering	Understand risk in modern techno-society, (Propose transparent policy on pipeline location and chemicals)	Petrochemical Industry adjusts their presumptions and value (Petrochemical industry cares about underground pipeline maintenances and holds conferences)	Create new energy /infrastructure/chemical industry solutions for sustainable society (Continuous dialogues between industry, government and academia)
Macro Relationship between society and engineering	Discuss Petro-chemical policy and transitional measures, (teach students with the case study)	Look at the relationship between petrochemical industry and local community, do progressive CSR (Judge expressed doubts about petrochemical company's CSR statement and policy)	Create new kind of petro-chemical industry, city, and citizen participation processes in public affair management (Industrial pipelines safety issues gain domestic recognition, technical discussion started)
Meso Institutional issues related to engineering and engineers/ organizations	Professional societies and education bodies discuss and include systematic causes into education (Chemical Engineering association offered workshop on pipeline safety)	Investigate the systematic problems in management, look into improvements in laws and regulations	Government and related agencies create new technologies or new institutes, operations (City government made information of the pipeline location open, established public roads construction information central office)
Micro Acts of individual engineers/ organizations	Professional societies and education bodies investigate the causes and teach the missing knowledge/abilities (teach students professional abilities, responsibilities, ethics with the case study)	Individual responses while on duty (The responsible person, engineers and technicians were prosecuted with criminal charges, trials are taking place currently)	Engineers and researchers act in developing and designing new technologies (Engineers and companies develop new surveying and monitoring technologies and tools)

*the level of shades represent the degree of attentions paid, darker means more discussion and more work was done.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper proposes a 4x3 GRID of Engineering Ethics as a framework for engineering ethics education. This comprehensive GRID includes levels from personal to societal in areas of education, industry and academia and allows the focus to start at any cell and stay aware of the others for discussion of Engineering Ethics in various contexts. The GRID helps to point out that the investigations and ongoing court processes

around the Kaohsiung pipeline explosion tend to focus on technical issues and miss out on the systematic and deeper causes of the problem. Possible changes in responsible engineering practices can therefore not be explored.

We will continue to research on engineering ethics, engineering education and controversies in engineering, aiming to develop directions on education transformation in a risk-based society. We hope to bring the attention of education government agency, higher education institutes, and industries to the existing gap between education, practice and creation of engineering.

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